

SCATTERING OF ANTI-PLANE SH-WAVE BY MULTIPLE CYLINDRICAL CAVITIES AND A LINEAR CRACK

H.L. Li^{1*}

¹ Department of Engineering Mechanics, Harbin Engineering University, Harbin ,150001, China

* Corresponding author(leehl@sina.com)

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1 Introduction

In natural medium, engineering materials and structures, it can be found that there are cavities everywhere. When structure is impacted by dynamic load, the scattering field will be produced because of the cavities, and it could cause dynamic stress concentration at the edge of the cavities. When the structure is overloaded or the load is changed regularly, cracks emerge and spread near the cavities. In theory of elastic wave motion, cavity and crack are two danger factor. Dynamic stress concentration could greatly decrease the bearing capacity of structure, and reduce the service life of structure.

In monograph of Pao(1973), it solved dynamic stress concentration problem in an infinite elastic space with a cavity by anti-plane SH wave, and it indicated that dynamic stress concentration factor is greater than static concentration factor. Datta(1974), Miklowitz(1978) and Moodie(1981) studied some correlative problems by different methods. The methods for solving such boundary value problems included wave function expansion, integral equation, integral transforms, matched asymptotic expansion. To regular shape cavity, wave function expansion method is more widely used. By applying the theory of complex function, Liu(1982) solved irregular shape cavity problem. On the other hand, dynamic stress intensity problems in an infinite elastic space with cracks were studied by several scientist. Through solving a system of coupled integral equations, Loeber and Sih(1968) studied dynamic stress intensity problem in an infinite elastic space with a finite crack by anti-plane shear wave, and gave numeric solution of dynamic stress intensity factor. By solving Cauchy singular integral equation, Achenbach(1981) did important work to this kind of problems. From 1980s, interaction of cavity or inclusion and crack in elastic space by SH wave was asked to study because of engineering problems. By

using perturbation method Coussy(1982) studied the problem of SH wave scattering by a cylindrical inclusion and an interface crack. By using integral equation method, Norris and Yang (1991) studied the influence of Static and dynamic axial load to a partially bonded fiber. Liu(1999) solved the problem of Scattering of SH-wave by Cracks Originating at A Circular Hole Edge and Dynamic Stress Intensity Factor. In this article, authors used Green's function and the technique of crack-division, and found that interaction of a cavity and a crack by SH wave must be considered in some cases. By using the same method, Liu and his student(2004) solved the problem of Scattering of SH-wave by an interface linear crack and a circular cavity near biomaterial interface. In doctoral dissertation, Li(2004) used Green's function, crack-division technique and assembly method to solve the problem of interaction of circular cavity, inclusion with beeline crack at arbitrary position by SH-wave. By using the same method, Li(2007) and Yang(2009) solved some correlative problems. So this method is effective.

Sometimes, there are some complex engineering problems. For example, there are two or more underground pipelines in city. Inevitably, there would be some crannies near the pipelines. So it is important to study the problem of scattering of elastic waves by multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack near the cavities. There are lots of materials obtained by theoretical research and earthquake damage investigation. These problems are complicated, It is hard to obtain analytic solutions except for several simple conditions [1,2].

In this paper, the method of Green's function is used to investigate the problem of dynamic stress concentration of multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack near the cavities for incident SH wave. Multi-polar coordinate system is used too, Which was used to solve the problem of interaction of

multiple semi-cylindrical canyons by plane SH-waves in anisotropic media by Liu(1993). The train of thoughts for this problem is that: Firstly, a Green's function is constructed for the problem, which is a fundamental solution of displacement field for an elastic space possessing multiple cylindrical cavities while bearing out-of-plane harmonic line source force at any point: Secondly, in terms of the solution of SH-wave's scattering by an elastic space with multiple cylindrical cavities, anti-plane stresses which are the same in quantity but opposite in direction to those mentioned before, are loaded at the region where the crack is in existent actually, this process is called "crack-division"; Finally, the expressions of the displacement and stresses are given when multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack exist at the same time. Then, by using the expressions, an example is studied to show the effect of crack on the dynamic stress concentration around cylindrical cavities.

2 Model and Green's function

The model is shown as Fig.1, elastic space containing multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack. In this paper, the anti-plane shear wave model is studied. The displacement is expressed as $W(x, y, t)$, and the displacement function W satisfies the following governing equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial y^2} + k^2 W = 0$$

where $k = \frac{\omega}{C_s}$, $C_s = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\rho}}$, ω is the circular frequency of the displacement $W(x, y, t)$, C_s stands for the shear wave velocity, ρ and μ are the mass density and the shear modulus of elasticity respectively.

Based on the complex function theory, the governing equation of W can also be written as

$$\frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial z \partial \bar{z}} + \frac{1}{4} k^2 W = 0$$

In polar coordinate system, the corresponding stresses are given by:

$$\tau_{rz} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial z} e^{i\theta} + \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{z}} e^{-i\theta} \right)$$

$$\tau_{\theta z} = \mu \left(\frac{\partial W}{\partial z} e^{i\theta} - \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{z}} e^{-i\theta} \right)$$

Fig.1. Model of the problem

The Green's function used in this paper is regarded as the displacement response to the elastic space containing multiple cylindrical cavities impacted by anti-plane harmonic linear source force at any point. The dependence of the displacement function G on time t is $e^{-i\omega t}$.

In complex plane, the governing equation of G can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial^2 G}{\partial z \partial \bar{z}} + \frac{1}{4} k^2 G = \delta(z - z_0) \quad (1)$$

The displacement in the elastic space is expressed as $G(z, \bar{z}, t)$, z_0 stands for the position of the linear source force in complex plane. The boundary conditions can be expressed as below:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{\theta z} &= \delta(z - z_0) \quad (z = z_0) \\ \tau_{rz} &= 0 \quad (|z - c_m| = R_m, m = 1, 2, \dots, N) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The basic solution which satisfies the control equation (1) and the boundary conditions (2) should include two parts of motion: the disturbance of anti-plane linear source force and the scattering wave incited by multiple cylindrical cavities. The wave displacement of the complete elastic space due to the

line source load $\delta(z - z_0)$ on the arbitrary position of the plane can be given:

$$G^{(i)} = \frac{i}{4\mu} H_0^{(1)}(k|z - z_0|) \quad (3)$$

The scattering wave incited by cavities can be written as:

$$G^{(s)} = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n^j H_n^{(1)}(k|z - c_j|) \left(\frac{z - c_j}{|z - c_j|} \right)^n \quad (4)$$

where A_n^j and B_n^m are unknown coefficients.

The wave field must satisfy the conditions on cavities, so by using the method of transferred coordinate, G can be written as:

$$G = \frac{i}{4\mu} H_0^{(1)}(k|z_m + c_m - z_0|) + \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n^j H_n^{(1)}(k|z_m - d_{mj}|) \left(\frac{z_m - d_{mj}}{|z_m - d_{mj}|} \right)^n$$

where $d_{mj} = c_j - c_m$.

And the boundary conditions could be changed to

$$\tau_{rz} = \tau_{r_m z}^{(i)} + \tau_{r_m z}^{(s)} = 0 \quad (|z_m| = R_m)$$

Substituting the wave field G to the boundary conditions, it can be obtained that

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n^j \varphi_{mn}^j = \varphi_m$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{mn}^j &= \frac{1}{2} \mu k A_n^j [H_{n-1}^{(1)}(k|z_m - d_{jm}|) \left(\frac{z_m - d_{jm}}{|z_m - d_{jm}|} \right)^{n-1} e^{i\theta_m} \\ &\quad - H_{n+1}^{(1)}(k|z_m - d_{jm}|) \left(\frac{z_m - d_{jm}}{|z_m - d_{jm}|} \right)^{n+1} e^{-i\theta_m}] \\ \varphi_m &= \frac{1}{8} ik H_1^{(1)}(k|z_m + c_m - z_0|) \left[\frac{z_m + c_m - z_0}{|z_m + c_m - z_0|} e^{i\theta_m} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{z_m + c_m - z_0}{|z_m + c_m - z_0|} e^{-i\theta_m} \right] \end{aligned}$$

By multiplying both sides of (7) with $e^{-im\theta_m}$ and integrating in interval $[-\pi, \pi]$, it can be obtained that

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} A_n^j \Psi_{mn}^j = \Psi_m \quad (5)$$

Where

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{mn}^j &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \varphi_{mn}^j e^{-im\theta_m} d\theta_m \\ \Psi_m &= \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \varphi_m e^{-im\theta_m} d\theta_m \end{aligned}$$

Equation (5) is a set of infinite algebraic equation for determining the coefficients A_n^j .

Substituting the coefficients A_n^j to Expression (4), the total wave field G of this problem can be obtained.

3 Expression of displacement and stress for the model

Firstly, we consider the incidence of SH-wave to the infinite linear elastic space containing multiple cylindrical cavities. The incident displacement field $W^{(i)}$ harmonic to time can be written as follows:

$$W^{(i)} = W_0 e^{ikr \cos(\theta - \alpha)} = W_0 e^{\frac{ik}{2}(ze^{-i\alpha} + \bar{z}e^{i\alpha})} \quad (6)$$

where α is the incident angle.

The scattering wave incited by cavities can be written as:

$$W^{(s)} = \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{n=-\infty}^{\infty} C_n^j H_n^{(1)}(k|z - c_j|) \left(\frac{z - c_j}{|z - c_j|} \right)^n \quad (7)$$

where C_n^j are unknown coefficients.

Therefore, the total wave field can be written as:

$$W^{(z)} = W^{(i)} + W^{(s)}$$

The boundary conditions can be expressed as below:

$$\tau_{rz}^{(i)} + \tau_{rz}^{(s)} = 0 \quad (|z - c_m| = R_m, m = 1, 2, \dots, N) \quad (8)$$

By using the same method which is used to confirm the unknown coefficients of the Green's function, the wave field $W^{(z)}$ can be obtained.

We consider the scattering problem of incident SH-wave when multiple cylindrical cavities and linear

crack exist at the same time. According to incident field and scattering field in the elastic space containing only multiple cylindrical cavities, the crack-division technique is used to construct the model of SH-wave scattering by an elastic space containing multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack[3,4].

The constructing process is that: the space is separated along the crack and a pair of anti-plane opposite forces with the multitude $-\tau_{\theta_z}^{(z)}$ are applied to up and down section of the region where crack will appear, therefore the resultant force on up (or down) section of the region is zero, which can be thought as crack. The above constructed Green's function indicates that the basic displacement solution can be obtained wherever the anti-plane linear source force's position it is. Consequently, we can obtain the total displacement field and stress field under the interaction of multiple cylindrical cavities and the crack for incident SH-wave. Hence, the total displacement and stress field can be written as follows:

$$W = W^{(i)} + W^{(s)} - \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \tau_{\theta_z}^{(z)} |_{z=z_0} \times G(z, z_0) dz_0$$

$$\tau_{\theta_z} = \tau_{\theta_z}^{(z)} - \int_{z_1}^{z_2} \tau_{\theta_z}^{(z)}(z_0) \cdot \tau_{\theta_z}^{(G)}(z, z_0) dz_0 \quad (9)$$

4 Example

In this paper, we pay attention to a representative kind of models. There are two cavities. The radius of the cavities equals 1, and the length of the crack is 2. The other parameters are shown in the figures. Fig.2 show the variation of dynamic stress concentration factor at the left cavity edge as the incident angle of SH-wave is 90° . Fig.3 show the variation of dynamic stress concentration factor at the left cavity edge as the incident angle of SH-wave is 0° . Compared with the condition there is only a cylindrical cavity, since there are a linear crack and another cavity, dynamic stress concentration factor at the left cavity edge is changed a lot. In Fig.4, the incident angle of SH-wave is changed from 0° to 90° . From the figure it can be found that when the incident angle is 90° the crack and another cavity have the largest influence to the dynamic stress concentration factor. In Fig.5, the distance between

the centre of the crack and the centre of the right cavity is changed from 3 to 12. It can be found that when the right cavity is removed from the left cavity, the influence can be negligible. From the instance above-said, it can be shown that the interaction of multiple cylindrical cavities and a linear crack should not be neglected.

5 Summary

In this paper, by using the technique of crack-division, a new method is given to solve the interaction problem of multiple cylindrical cavities and a Linear Crack by incident SH-wave. By using the method an example is solved, and some new conclusion is given. The method in the paper could be used to study some other correlative problem.

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Fig.2. Influence of crack and right cavity($\alpha = 90^\circ$)

Fig.3. Influence of crack and right cavity ($\alpha = 0^\circ$)

Fig.5. Influence of right cavity

Fig.4 influence of incident angle